

Electrochemical detection of fusion genes: Advancing cancer diagnosis and therapy

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Fusion genes
Electrochemical detection
Precision oncology
Cancer biomarker
DNA analysis

ABSTRACT

Fusion genes are formed by joining segments of two different genes through translocations, deletions, chromosomal insertions, or aberrant gene splicing. These fusions, detectable at the DNA, RNA, and protein levels, are diagnostically and prognostically relevant molecular indices for the selection of targeted therapies, monitoring of minimal residual disease after treatment, and prediction of relapse. In contrast to traditional determination techniques, electroanalytical technologies provide affordable, versatile, portable, and rapid detection methods that do not compromise specificity, sensitivity, robustness, or accuracy. These advantages make them highly promising for advancing research, enabling clinical adoption, supporting pharmaceutical development, and expanding access to accurate diagnostics and effective therapies. In this context, this review article addresses the potential and opportunities offered by electroanalytical technologies for fusion gene detection. It provides a brief description of the most common fusion genes in hematological malignancies and solid tumors, an explanation of frequently used standard techniques, a critical overview of recent electrochemical (EC)-based studies targeting the most common fusion genes, and highlights the challenges faced by current EC bioassays.

1. Introduction

Fusion genes arise from chromosomal rearrangements, that is, structural alterations in a chromosome that have a serious impact on gene function or expression. These are mostly translocations, where a segment of one chromosome breaks off and attaches either to different sites on the same chromosome (intrachromosomal translocation) or to a different chromosome (interchromosomal translocation) [1]. Other chromosomal rearrangements, besides translocations, include inversions (i.e., reversed orientation of a chromosome segment), duplications (extra copies of a chromosome segment), and deletions (loss of a chromosome segment). The most common examples of these rearrangements are listed in Table 1. Previously, chromosomal aberrations were thought to be the only mechanism by which fusion products are generated. Later, it became clear that some fusion products could arise without structural chromosomal rearrangements – through the aberrant splicing of genes. These genetic alterations play pivotal roles in the

development and progression of a wide range of diseases. While some of these alterations are linked to rare syndromes, such as Norrie disease retinopathy, Pallister-Killian syndrome, and Potocki-Shaffer syndrome, they are especially significant in the context of cancer [2–5].

In oncology, these genetic changes often serve as both diagnostic markers and therapeutic targets. The oncogenic potential of fusion genes often arises from their ability to produce abnormally active proteins – typically tyrosine kinases (TKs) or transcription factors [6]. A prime example is the *BCR::ABL1* fusion gene, best known for its association with the Philadelphia chromosome in chronic myeloid leukemia (CML). While tyrosine kinases drive uncontrolled cellular signaling, fusion transcription factors disrupt normal gene regulation, contributing to tumorigenesis.

In addition to signaling and transcription, some fusion proteins affect cellular architecture by altering the cytoskeleton, thus influencing cell migration [7,8]. These structural disruptions can enhance the invasiveness of cancer cells [9]. In some cases, fusion genes promote

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epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT), a process critical for tumor metastasis. By regulating cytoskeletal remodeling, EMT-related fusions enable cancer cells to detach from the primary tumor and invade surrounding tissues [10]. Additionally, fusion proteins may interfere with the key regulatory pathways that govern the cell cycle, differentiation, and apoptosis. When these controls break down, cancer cells can proliferate unchecked and evade programmed cell death, further contributing to tumor growth and resistance to treatment [11]. Fusion gene analysis thus plays a critical role in oncology by enabling precise molecular classification of tumors, which is essential for selecting targeted therapies. Identifying specific fusion events can directly guide the use of approved pharmaceutical agents, as described in Table 1.

Given the importance and increasing number of identified fusion genes, novel methods and technologies are needed for their analysis. Recently, electrochemical (EC) techniques have emerged as promising alternatives for detecting DNA cancer biomarkers [12–16] because they offer rapid detection times, cost-effective and simple instrumentation, and the capability for parallel detection on miniaturized electrode chips. Several recent reviews have appeared [17–21], but they deal exclusively with the application of EC techniques in leukemia detection (mostly *BCR::ABL1* fusion gene). To our knowledge, there is no comprehensive review of EC studies for the detection of various fusion genes and transcripts in both hematological malignancies as well as solid tumors. Moreover, no review has combined the biological relevance of fusion genes (leukemia, see Section 2, and solid tumors, Section 3), standard methods of detection (Section 4), and critical review of recent EC-based studies as powerful alternatives to these methods, targeting the most prevalent fusion genes and describing the challenges faced by current EC bioassays (Section 5).

2. Fusion genes in leukemia

Fusion genes are hallmarks of many leukemias and often drive disease development through chromosomal rearrangements in hematopoietic progenitor cells. The resulting fusion proteins frequently exhibit

oncogenic properties that disrupt gene expression, cell cycle regulation and DNA repair. A key example is the above-mentioned *BCR::ABL1* fusion in CML, which produces abnormal TKs essential for leukemogenesis. Currently, approximately 50 recurrent fusion genes are linked to leukemia, and new ones are continually being identified. While some fusions are shared across leukemia subtypes - CML, acute myeloid leukemia (AML), chronic lymphocytic leukemia (CLL), and acute lymphoblastic leukemia (ALL) - each disease typically harbors distinct recurrent fusion genes. The most significant leukemogenic fusions are discussed below.

The *BCR::ABL1* fusion is an oncogene present in over 95% of CML cases [38,39], making it the defining genetic abnormality of the disease, although it also occurs in the B-cell ALL subtype (in approximately 3–6% of pediatric cases and 25–40% of adult cases) [40,41]. This fusion encodes a constitutively active TK that drives cell proliferation, survival, and apoptosis resistance by activating pathways such as RAS, PI3K, and STAT5. Its presence is crucial for diagnosis and serves as a therapeutic target for tyrosine kinase inhibitors (TKIs), such as imatinib [42]. The *BCR::ABL1* fusion gene exhibits breakpoint variability, resulting in different isoforms with distinct clinical implications (Fig. 1). The most common *BCR::ABL1* fusion isoform, p210, is typically associated with CML. It results from a fusion between *BCR* exon 13 (e13, also called b2) or exon 14 (e14, also called b3) on chromosome 22 and *ABL1* exon 2 (a2) on chromosome 9. These fusions are designated as e13a2 (b2a2) and e14a2 (b3a2), respectively. This isoform generally responds well to first-generation TKIs, such as imatinib. In contrast, the shorter p190 isoform, arising from a breakpoint in *BCR* exon 1 (e1) fused to *ABL1* exon 2 (a2), designated e1a2, is more commonly found in Philadelphia chromosome-positive ALL and is often associated with reduced sensitivity to imatinib, potentially requiring more potent or second-generation TKIs. Less common variants, such as p230 (*BCR* exon 19 fusion) and p180 (*BCR* exon 16 fusion), also exist. Identifying the specific *BCR::ABL1* variant is critical for tailoring treatment, as the breakpoint location can influence oncogenic potential, therapeutic response, and prognosis [43].

Table 1

List of most common fusion genes implicated in various types of tumors.

Fusion gene ¹	Rearrangement	Type of cancer	Standard therapy	Ref.
<i>BCR::ABL1</i>	t(9;22) ² (q34;q11) ³	CML ⁴ , ALL ⁵	TK inhibitors (imatinib, ponatinib, dasatinib)	[22]
<i>ETV6::RUNX1</i>	t(12;21)(p13;q22) ⁶	ALL	N/A	[23]
<i>PML::RARA</i>	t(15;17)(q24;q21)	AML ⁷ (M3 ⁸)	all-trans retinoic acid, arsenic trioxide	[24]
<i>MLL::AF4, AF9, ENL, ELL</i>	t(4;11), t(9;11), t(11;19) (q23;p13.3), t(11;19) (q23;p13.1)	ALL	N/A	[25]
<i>RUNX1::RUNX1T1</i>	t(8;21)(q22;q22)	AML (M2 ⁸)	cytarabine + daunorubicin	[26]
<i>EWSR1::FLI1</i>	t(11;22)(q24;q12)	Ewing's sarcoma	N/A	[27]
<i>ETV6::NTRK3</i>	t(12;15)(p13;q25)	congenital fibrosarcoma, congenital mesoblastic nephroma, secretory breast carcinoma	TRK inhibitors (larotrectinib, entrectinib)	[28–30]
<i>EML4::ALK</i>	inv(2) ⁹ (p21p23)	NSCLC ¹⁰	ALK inhibitors (crizotinib, ceritinib, alectinib, brigatinib, lorlatinib)	[31]
<i>KIF5B::RET</i>	inv(10)(p11q11)	lung adenocarcinoma	RET inhibitors (selpercatinib, pralsetinib)	[32]
<i>BRAF::KIAA1549</i>	dup ¹¹ (7)(q34q34)	pilocytic astrocytoma	MEK inhibitors (selumetinib)	[33]
<i>FGFR3::TACC3</i>	dup(4)(p16p16)	glioblastoma, bladder cancer	FGFR inhibitors (erdafitinib, futibatinib, pemigatinib)	[34,35]
<i>TMPRSS2::ERG</i>	del ¹² (21)(q22q22)	prostate cancer	N/A	[36]

¹ The HUGO Gene Nomenclature Committee recommends using the double colon (::) to describe gene fusions [37]. This aligns with the The International System for Human Cytogenomics Nomenclature (ISCN), where a single colon (:) signifies a chromosome break, and a double colon (::) indicates a break and reunion

² t - translocation

³ q - long arm of chromosomes

⁴ CML - chronic myeloid leukemia

⁵ ALL - acute lymphoblastic leukemia

⁶ p - short arm of chromosomes

⁷ AML - acute myeloid leukemia

⁸ M0–M7 are subtypes of AML classified according to the French-American-British classification system

⁹ inv - inversion

¹⁰ NSCLC - non-small-cell lung cancer

¹¹ dup - duplication

¹² del - deletion.

Fig. 1. Simplified scheme showing $t(9;22)$ translocation forming the Philadelphia chromosome. Breakpoints in the *BCR* gene (e1/exon 1, b2/exon 13, b3/exon 14, e19/exon 19) and *ABL1* gene (a2/exon 2) generate different *BCR::ABL1* fusion transcripts. Common isoforms include e1a2, b2a2, b3a2, and a less common e19a2 variant, each associated with distinct hematologic malignancies.

Acute promyelocytic leukemia (APL), a distinct AML subtype, is defined by the *PML::RARA* fusion gene resulting from $t(15;17)$ translocation. The *PML::RARA* chimeric protein disrupts PML's role in apoptosis and impairs promyelocyte differentiation, driving leukemogenesis [44,45]. Rare alternative *RARA* fusions, such as *GTF2L::RARA* and *ZBTB16::RARA*, can occur in APL and are typically resistant to standard therapies [46,47].

The *MLL* gene (11q23) is frequently rearranged in both ALL and AML, forming fusion proteins with partners such as *AF4*, *AF9*, *ENL*, and *ELL*. The *MLL* gene encodes a key regulator of gene expression in hematopoiesis, and its fusion with other genes disrupts transcriptional control and chromatin modification, thereby driving leukemogenesis. *MLL* fusion-positive leukemia is typically aggressive, therapy-resistant, and associated with a poor prognosis. While *MLL* fusions occur in both infants and adults, they are more common in childhood leukemia [25].

The *ETV6::RUNX1* fusion gene is one of the most common genetic alterations in pediatric ALL and serves as a key diagnostic marker for this disease. This fusion disrupts normal hematopoietic differentiation and promotes leukemogenesis by altering the gene expression. *RUNX1*, a crucial transcription factor in blood cell development, loses its function when fused with *ETV6*, leading to the accumulation of abnormal

lymphoid cells. Despite its role in leukemogenesis, *ETV6::RUNX1*-positive ALL generally responds well to chemotherapy and is associated with a favorable prognosis [23].

3. Fusion genes in solid tumors

For a long time, fusion genes were believed to be found almost exclusively in hematopoietic diseases, such as leukemia. Their presence in solid tumors has been largely overlooked, and only a few researchers have actively searched for them in solid tumors. This changed in 1992 when the *EWSR1::FLI1* fusion gene was identified in Ewing sarcoma [48]. Subsequently, fusion genes have been discovered in other sarcomas, as well as in prostate, lung, breast carcinomas, and gliomas [49–52].

Ewing sarcoma is a bone and soft tissue cancer that primarily affects children and adolescents. Resistance to conventional therapies is common; thus, there is an urgent need to develop targeted treatments for this disease [53]. Approximately 85% of Ewing sarcoma cases have the *EWSR1::FLI1* fusion. In the remaining cases, the *EWSR1* gene is usually found to be fused with other members of the *ETS* family [48,54]. *EWSR1::FLI1* most commonly arises from the $t(11;22)(q24;q12)$

translocation, which fuses the strong transcriptional activation domain of the RNA-binding protein EWSR1 with the DNA-binding domain of FLI. This leads to the formation of an abnormal transcription factor involved in tumorigenesis and tumor progression.

Prostate cancer is the second most common solid malignancy in men and the fifth most frequent cause of cancer-related deaths worldwide [55]. For a long time, the only diagnostic biomarker employed was prostate-specific antigen (PSA). However, elevated PSA level may not necessarily indicate prostate cancer, as it may also be associated with benign prostatic hyperplasia. In 2005, Tomlins et al. detected recurrent fusions of *TMPRSS2* with either *ERG* or *ETV1* (both ETS family transcription factors) in prostate cancer tissue. *TMPRSS2* is a transmembrane serine protease regulated by androgens. When fused to *ERG* or *ETV1*, its androgen-responsive promoter drives overexpression of these transcription factors [56]. *TMPRSS2::ERG* is present in more than half of the prostate cancer cases and in some breast cancer cases. Aberrant *ERG* expression has been demonstrated to lead to increased angiogenesis and, thus, cancer development [57]. Although the prognostic significance of this fusion is controversial, there is a probable association between increased *ERG* expression and tumor stage [58].

Another fusion gene identified in solid tumors is *EML4::ALK*, which is present in approximately 5% of NSCLC cases. This fusion gene was first discovered in 2007 and is predominantly found in non-smokers or light smokers [59,60]. Patients with this fusion gene typically respond well to ALK TKI, but resistance inevitably emerges, with certain variants being more strongly associated with treatment failure. Therefore, genotyping these variants is beneficial for selecting the most appropriate drug [61].

Different tumor groups involve the fusion of genes from the *NTRK* family (*NTRK1*, *NTRK2*, or *NTRK3*). Genes from this group encode neurotrophin receptors (TrkA, TrkB, TrkC, respectively), and their fusions with other genes typically result in the activation of their kinase subunit in the absence of ligand binding [62]. This phenomenon leads to the aberrant activation of signaling pathways that regulate cell growth and survival, as well as those involved in tumor development and progression [63]. A significant number of tumors with *NTRK* fusion respond well to TKIs, such as larotrectinib or entrectinib [64]. Resistance may arise primarily from mutations in the kinase subunit of *NTRK*; however, next-generation TRK inhibitors have shown promising efficacy [65]. The best-known of these is the *ETV6::NTRK3* fusion found in congenital fibrosarcoma and other neoplasms, including human secretory breast carcinoma and salivary gland secretory carcinoma [29,66,67]. Additionally, other fusions involving genes from the *NTRK* group have been documented in various lesions, such as papillary thyroid carcinoma and gliomas [68,69].

In gliomas, *BRAF* (especially the *BRAF::KIAA1549* fusion) is frequently identified in fusions. It may also be present in melanoma, lung adenocarcinoma, and other tumors. *BRAF* encodes a serine-threonine kinase that is part of the mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) – extracellular signal-regulated kinase (ERK) signaling pathway [70,71]. *BRAF* fusions result in the constant activation of the kinase domain, leading to excessive signaling and cell proliferation [72]. This type of fusion is most commonly observed in pilocytic astrocytoma (a low-grade glioma), where it has a favorable prognostic impact [73].

4. Standard methods of detection

The detection of fusion genes is essential for the molecular stratification of tumors and the classification of their subtypes [74], with significant implications for treatment response, prognosis, and overall survival [75,76]. Advances in chromosomal banding techniques in the 1950s led to the discovery of the first chromosomal and genetic rearrangements [77]. Over the years, other methods for detecting fusion genes have emerged, such as immunohistochemistry (IHC) and fluorescent *in situ* hybridization (FISH). Furthermore, reverse transcription-polymerase chain reaction (RT-qPCR) has become an important tool for detecting fusion transcripts. The introduction of deep

sequencing has revolutionized the field, uncovering thousands of fusion gene variants and identifying new potential drug targets that have advanced to clinical trials [74]. The advantages and disadvantages of these methods are presented in Table 2.

However, the detection of fusion genes can be challenging, particularly when dealing with rare variants, promiscuous fusion partners, or atypical breakpoints [78–80]. Selecting the correct diagnostic method requires careful consideration of factors such as the type and quality of the tested sample, prior knowledge of fusion partners and their breakpoints, and the potential added benefits of identifying previously unknown fusion partners [81]. Equally important is the consideration of how real-world clinical samples are collected, processed, and prepared, as these pre-analytical steps critically influence the success and reliability of downstream diagnostic methods. In hematological malignancies such as leukemia, peripheral blood or bone marrow aspirates are commonly collected [82], whereas in solid tumors, samples are obtained by biopsy or surgical resection, or alternatively through liquid biopsy of blood, urine, or saliva for circulating tumor DNA (ctDNA) analysis [83, 84]. For molecular methods such as RT-qPCR or RNA sequencing, total RNA is extracted (e.g., using silica column-based kits or TRIzol) and its quality is assessed before reverse transcription into complementary DNA (cDNA), which serves as the template for amplification [82]. In contrast, cytogenetic approaches such as FISH or karyotyping analyze intact cells or nuclei fixed on slides, enabling direct visualization of chromosomal rearrangements without RNA extraction or amplification [85].

The first evidence pointing to the existence of fusion genes dates back to 1960, when Nowell and Hungerford observed ‘minute chromosomes’ in leukocytes of leukemia patients using early karyotyping techniques [77]. Improved resolution has allowed a better understanding of chromosomes and their rearrangements, leading to groundbreaking discoveries in the 1970s and beyond [86].

Karyotyping is a technique for visualizing chromosomes via metaphase spreads but has notable limitations [87]. This approach requires the culturing of living cells, which can be challenging in the case of tumor cells. Additionally, balanced translocations and chromosomal aberrations smaller than 5 Mb may not be detected [88].

FISH is currently considered the gold standard for detecting fusion genes because of its quick turnaround time, high sensitivity, and specificity [89]. This method is based on the hybridization of a DNA probe labeled with fluorophores to a complementary DNA region. Two FISH approaches are commonly used for the detection of fusion genes. With split-signal probes, the suspected gene is labeled with a red fluorophore at the 5' end and a green fluorophore at the 3' end (or vice versa). In intact cells, the acquired signals are in close proximity and can thus be observed as yellow, whereas in fusion genes, they are distinct from each other. In contrast, fusion-signal probes are based on fusion partners labeled with green and red. If a fusion gene is present, it appears yellow; otherwise, two different signals are observed [88,89]. Unlike karyotyping, FISH does not require metaphase cells, making this approach more accessible [88]. FISH also does not require prior knowledge of

Table 2
Advantages and disadvantages of different approaches in detecting fusion genes.

Method	Biomolecule target	Advantages	Disadvantages
Karyotyping	DNA	Cost-effective	Low resolution and long turnaround time
IHC	Protein	Cost-effective	Limited availability of reliable antibodies
FISH	DNA	Widely available, high sensitivity	Costly, low resolution
RT-qPCR	RNA	Rapid, low-cost, high sensitivity	Necessary prior knowledge of fusion partners
Sequencing	DNA or RNA	High accuracy, no previous knowledge of fusion partners required	Costly, complex data processing

fusion partners but is usually restricted to the detection of the most common gene rearrangements [90]. Although traditional FISH is not suitable for whole-genome screening, its modifications, such as spectral karyotyping (SKY), multicolor FISH, comparative genomic hybridization (CGH), and array-CGH, help to overcome this limitation. However, these modifications are not widely used in clinical practice [88].

IHC is a fast and widely available technique that allows direct visualization of fusion proteins in tumor cells [91]. The most common approach involves antibodies targeting the N-terminus and C-terminus of the wild-type protein, which detects the fusion protein when only partial expression is observed [92]. IHC is cost-effective and requires minimal starting materials [93]. Its limitations include the restricted availability of specific antibodies and sensitivity to proper sample handling, particularly tissue fixation [94]. IHC is used to detect fusion proteins in solid tumors (for example, NTRK fusions) but is not applicable to leukemia [95].

RT-qPCR uses specific primers to detect fusion transcripts, primarily in leukemia samples. Primer design for RT-qPCR requires prior knowledge of both fusion partners and their exon breakpoints, which in turn leads to high sensitivity. However, this can be seen as a double-edged sword, as it limits its application to common variants [96]. While RT-qPCR enables the quantification of fusion transcripts, it should be considered a complementary method, particularly when IHC and FISH results are discordant. Both FISH and RT-qPCR can miss fusion genes with atypical breakpoints [97,98].

Next generation sequencing (NGS) is a high-throughput technique that sequences small DNA or RNA fragments in a massively parallel fashion, allowing for the simultaneous testing of multiple known or unknown genes in a single run. This has led to the identification of approximately 90% of all known fusion gene variants [74]. However, its main limitations include the high cost of the new sequencing system and the required reagents [90]. Additionally, complex data processing, long turnaround times, and the need for sufficient starting material can be challenging in clinical practice [81]. Recently, the costs of commercially available gene panels have significantly reduced, making sequencing more accessible in healthcare settings. Targeted panels typically use amplicon-based or hybrid-capture methods. Hybrid-capture approaches rely on the hybridization of biotin-labeled probes to the gene of interest, whereas amplicon-based methods involve the PCR amplification of a specific region of interest [99,100]. A recent study has shown that panels based on RNA sequencing have higher sensitivity and lead to fewer false negatives than DNA-based panels [101].

NGS can sequence RNA and DNA, each with a specific approach, and can be applied to genomes, exomes, transcriptomes, and more. RNA sequencing detects and quantifies transcriptionally active fusion genes, thus identifying driver mutations leading to cancer progression and excluding passenger fusions [93]. RNA-based probes are easier to design because of fixed fusion breakpoints [102]. RNA sequencing is not affected by intronic regions and can distinguish splicing isoforms [103], although RNA degradation (especially in formalin-fixed tissue samples) may affect the accuracy of the results [104]. However, RNA sequencing is not yet applicable to blood samples [102].

DNA sequencing is more stable than RNA approaches and can precisely identify fusion breakpoints, single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs), copy number variants (CNVs), and other genomic alterations [105]. Deep coverage and longer reads are necessary for precise data, as introns with similar repeated sequences can affect detection accuracy [102]. DNA probes target exonic, intronic, and intergenic regions [106, 107], whereas RNA probes specifically target exonic regions [108]. Whole-genome sequencing is the most comprehensive option; however, its high cost and time-consuming nature make its implementation in clinical practice difficult. Whole-exome sequencing significantly reduces costs; however, its potential use is severely limited because the majority of fusions occur in introns [93,109].

5. Electrochemical methods for fusion gene analysis

EC detection offers a cost-effective, rapid, and highly sensitive approach for cancer biomarker detection, with simplified instrumentation, low sample consumption, and potential for point-of-care applications. EC biosensing in cancer research has been a fruitful area of study, targeting both nucleic acids and proteins as tumor biomarkers [12, 110–118]. Regarding nucleic acids, many papers have appeared in recent years describing novel strategies for the analysis of non-coding RNAs [119–122], DNA methylation [123–125], DNA point mutations [15,126,127], oncoviral sequences [116,128,129], and ctDNA [130]. Although less frequent, several EC studies have also reported fusion gene detection, mostly of the *BCR::ABL1* fusion gene, but also of other genes (Table 3 and reviewed in [17–20]). Most often, techniques such as cyclic voltammetry (CV), differential pulse voltammetry (DPV), electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) or amperometry have been used across studies to measure hybridization events or enzymatic reactions, enabling the sensitive and specific detection of various fusion genes. Each of these EC techniques has distinct advantages and limitations in biosensing applications. CV provides rapid insight into redox processes and surface modifications, although its sensitivity is limited for low-abundance biomarkers. DPV offers much higher sensitivity by reducing background currents; however, the measurements take longer and are more susceptible to variability. EIS enables highly sensitive and label-free detection, albeit with longer acquisition times and the need for careful modeling. Amperometry stands out as the most successfully translated EC technique from academia to industry, offering simple, real-time, and highly sensitive detection; however, it is generally restricted to single analyte determination and can be affected by interferents in complex samples. Here, we review recent advances in EC biosensors applied to fusion gene analysis, noting each study's contributions, strengths, and limitations, particularly focusing on whether real samples were used.

When working with real samples, an enzymatic pre-amplification step is usually required, mostly with PCR or its variants. For instance, Chen et al. [131] and Lin et al. [132] used PCR products of the *BCR::ABL1* fusion gene to evaluate their EC DNA biosensors, utilizing locked nucleic acid (LNA) probes for improved selectivity. LNA-modified probes are particularly effective in distinguishing single-base mismatches and are thus of great value in detecting mutations linked to CML. In Chen's study [131], the biosensor featured an LNA-modified capture probe covalently attached to a glassy carbon electrode modified with 4-aminobenzenesulfonic acid. This setup promoted selective hybridization between the capture probe and target DNA, forming a double-stranded DNA (dsDNA) structure that was detectable by DPV using methylene blue (MB) as an EC indicator. Upon hybridization, the DPV peak current of MB decreased because of the restricted access to guanine bases in dsDNA. This current reduction was directly proportional to the target DNA concentration, allowing for the quantitative detection of the *BCR::ABL1* fusion gene. This approach emphasizes a straightforward covalent attachment method, resulting in stable probe immobilization and sensitivity to target DNA concentration. However, the authors used only two real samples (one positive and one negative, without any details) and a single PCR product from the K562 cell line (a positive control for the b3a2 variant), limiting their study by restricting the evaluation of assay performance across a wider range of clinical samples and reducing the ability to demonstrate robustness under diverse conditions. Similarly, Lin's biosensor [132] used a hairpin-structured LNA probe on a gold electrode, which was modified through sulfur-gold interactions to enhance probe stability. The hairpin configuration of the LNA probe adds an additional level of structural specificity, improving its ability to detect mutations with single-base precision. After hybridization, Lin's biosensor monitored changes in the EC signals via DPV, with MB serving as the electroactive indicator. The observed decrease in the peak current signaled successful hybridization, and the hairpin structure provided a unique advantage by further

Table 3
Main features of EC biosensors and biosays reported for fusion genes or transcripts detection.

Fundamentals	Technique	Fusion gene/transcript (Disease)	Linear Range/LOD ¹	Application	Ref.
Hybridization at immobilized DNA probe on a GCE ²	DPV ³ (MB ⁴)	<i>BCR::ABL1</i> fusion gene (CML)	1.25×10^{-7} – 6.75×10^{-7} M/ 5.9×10^{-8} M	–	[150]
Sandwich hybridization of branched DNA-amplified target, CP ⁵ immobilized at a SPE	SWV ⁶ (AP/1-NP)	<i>p185 BCR::ABL1</i> fusion transcript (ALL)	2.2×10^5 – 1.6×10^8 copies/ 6.1×10^4 copies	mRNA from SUP-B15 cells	[151]
Hybridization on LNA ⁷ probe immobilized at a 4-ABSA-modified GCE	DPV (MB)	<i>BCR::ABL1</i> fusion gene (CML)	1.0×10^{-12} – 1.1×10^{-11} M/ 9.4×10^{-13} M	PCR products from a positive real sample and K562 cells	[131]
Hybridization at immobilized DNA probe on a GCE	DPV (STS ⁸)	<i>BCR::ABL1</i> fusion gene (CML)	2.0×10^{-8} – 2.0×10^{-7} M/ 6.7×10^{-9} M	cDNA from CML patients	[152]
Hybridization on a thiolated hairpin LNA probe assembled on AuE ⁹	DPV (MB)	<i>BCR::ABL1</i> fusion gene (CML)	-1.2×10^{-10} M	PCR products from a positive real sample	[132]
Sandwich hybridization assay using a thiolated LNA probe assembled on an AuE and a biotinylated reported probe	Chronoamperometry (HRP ¹⁰ /TMB ¹¹ /H ₂ O ₂)	<i>BCR::ABL1</i> fusion gene (CML)	–/–	PCR products from K562 cells	[153]
Hybridization at thiolated-hairpin LNA probe assembled on a AuNPs/AuE	DPV (CuR ₂ ¹²)	<i>BCR::ABL1</i> fusion gene (CML)	-1.0×10^{-10} M	PCR products from real samples	[154]
Hybridization at thiolated DNA probe assembled on a GNPs ¹³ / MWCNTs ¹⁴ /CeO ₂ -CS/GCE	DPV (MB)	<i>BCR::ABL1</i> fusion gene (CML)	1×10^{-9} – 1×10^{-12} M/ 5×10^{-13} M	PCR products from real samples	[155]
Hybridization at DNA probe immobilized on GNPs/PANI ¹⁵ -modified AuE	EIS ¹⁶ ([Fe(CN) ₆] ^{3-/4-})	<i>BCR::ABL1</i> fusion gene (ALL)	-6.94×10^{-17} M	cDNA from ALL patients	[136]
Hybridization at DNA probe immobilized at a CS-CdTe/ITO ¹⁷ electrode	DPV (MB)	<i>BCR::ABL1</i> fusion gene (CML)	1×10^{-6} – 1×10^{-11} M/ 1×10^{-12} M	cDNA from CML patients	[156]
Hybridization at thiolated DNA probe assembled on a QcCdSe-SA-LB ¹⁸ /ITO electrode	DPV (MB)	<i>BCR::ABL1</i> fusion gene (CML)	Up to 1.0×10^{-6} M/ 1.0×10^{-14} M	cDNA from CML patients	[157]
Hybridization at thiolated molecular beacon probe assembled on an AuE, CSRP ¹⁹ combining cascade hybridization and QDs ²⁰ tagging	ASV ²¹ (Cd)	<i>BCR::ABL1</i> fusion gene (CML)	1.0×10^{-14} – 1.0×10^{-10} M/ 2×10^{-16} M	–	[158]
Hybridization at thiolated DNA probe assembled at a biosynthesized AuNPs/poly(catechol)/GS/GCE	DPV (Catechol)	<i>BCR::ABL1</i> fusion gene (ALL)	1.0×10^{-4} – 1.0×10^{-11} M/ 1.0×10^{-12} M	PCR products from real samples	[159]
Hybridization at DNA probe immobilized at a FePt/ERGNOC ²² /CPE	EIS ([Fe(CN) ₆] ^{3-/4-})	<i>BCR::ABL1</i> fusion gene (CML)	1.0×10^{-14} – 1.0×10^{-9} M/ 2.6×10^{-15} M	PCR products from real samples	[160]
Hybridization at immobilized DNA probe on a GCE	DPV (ISO ²³)	<i>BCR::ABL1</i> fusion gene (CML)	1.0×10^{-11} – 5.0×10^{-7} M/ 3.0×10^{-12} M	–	[161]
Hybridization with thiolated and biotinylated hairpin probe at a AuNPs/PANI/CS-GS/GCE	DPV (AP+1-NP)	<i>BCR::ABL1</i> fusion gene (CML)	1.0×10^{-11} – 1.0×10^{-9} M/ 2.11×10^{-12} M	PCR products from a positive real sample and K562 cells	[162]
Hybridization at biotinylated DNA probe immobilized on PANI-MoS ₂ /ITO bioelectrode	EIS ([Fe(CN) ₆] ^{3-/4-})	<i>BCR::ABL1</i> fusion gene (CML)	1.0×10^{-6} – 1.0×10^{-17} M/ 3×10^{-18} M	cDNA from CML patients	[163]
Dual detection mode, hybridization at DNA probe immobilized on Hb@AuNCs ²⁴ -GS/AuNPs modified GCE	“Signal on”: EIS ([Fe(CN) ₆] ^{3-/4-}) Signal off: DPV (MB)	<i>BCR::ABL1</i> fusion gene (CML)	“Signal on”: 1.0×10^{-16} – 1.0×10^{-11} M/ 3.7×10^{-17} M, “Signal off”: 1.0×10^{-16} – 1.0×10^{-11} M/ 3.0×10^{-17} M	cDNA from CML patients	[164]
Sandwich hybridization at thiolated capture probe assembled on AuNPs/Ti ₃ C ₂ T _x MXene/GCE, biotinylated reported probe and DNA walking machine (DNA-Au@Fe ₃ O ₄)	DPV (AP+1-NP)	<i>BCR::ABL1</i> fusion gene (CML)	2.0×10^{-16} – 2.0×10^{-8} M/ 5.0×10^{-17} M	Supplemented human serum samples	[165]
Split-type EC biosensor using enzyme-linked DNA magnetic beads and duplex LCR ²⁵ coupled with OR logic gate design	Amperometry (HRP/TMB/H ₂ O ₂)	<i>BCR::ABL1</i> ²¹⁰ transcript (CML)	1.0×10^{-18} – 5.0×10^{-14} M and 1.0×10^{-15} – 1.0×10^{-12} M/ 1.0×10^{-18} M	cDNA from CML patients	[133]
ZnO/PICA ²⁶ nanocomposite for DNA immobilization	EIS PICA/ZnO	<i>BCR::ABL1</i> fusion gene (CML)	1.0×10^{-15} – 1.0×10^{-9} M/ 2.2×10^{-16} M	synthetic oligonucleotide sequences that mimic the <i>BCR::ABL1</i> fusion gene	[139]
Fe ₃ O ₄ nanoparticles functionalized CNTs ²⁷	EIS using [Fe(CN) ₆] ^{3-/4-} as redox probe	<i>BCR::ABL1</i> fusion gene (CML)	1.0×10^{-13} – 1.0×10^{-9} M/ 3.3×10^{-14} M	synthetic oligonucleotide sequences that mimic the <i>BCR::ABL1</i> fusion gene	[138]
PICA-functionalized ZnO nanostructure	EIS	<i>BCR::ABL1</i> fusion gene (CML)	Not specified/ 1.0×10^{-16} M	synthetic oligonucleotide sequences that mimic the <i>BCR::ABL1</i> fusion gene	[166]
Hybridization at immobilized DNA probe on a GCE	DPV (AE)	<i>PML::RARA</i> fusion gene (APL)	1.5×10^{-8} – 1.5×10^{-7} M/ 6.7×10^{-8} M	–	[167]
Hybridization at immobilized DNA probe on a poly-CCA ²⁸ film modified GCE	DPV (MB)	<i>PML::RARA</i> fusion gene (APL)	1.0×10^{-12} – 1.0×10^{-11} M/ 6.7×10^{-13} M	–	[168]

(continued on next page)

Table 3 (continued)

Fundamentals	Technique	Fusion gene/transcript (Disease)	Linear Range/LOD ¹	Application	Ref.
Hybridization on hairpin LNA probe dually labeled with biotin and FAM immobilized at a streptavidin-poly-CCA-GCE	Chronoamperometry (HRP/TMB/H ₂ O ₂)	<i>PML::RARA</i> fusion gene (APL)	In 20% serum: 1.0×10^{-12} – 1.0×10^{-7} M/ 8.3×10^{-14} M	PCR products from NB4 cells and a positive real sample	[144]
Hybridization at immobilized DNA probe on an aldehyde-agarose hydrogel-modified GCE	DPV (MB)	<i>PML::RARA</i> fusion gene (APL)	4.0×10^{-12} – 1.2×10^{-11} M/ 4.0×10^{-12} M	–	[169]
Hybridization at thiolated DNA probe assembled on a NPG electrode	DPV (MB)	<i>PML::RARA</i> fusion gene (APL)	6.0×10^{-11} – 2.2×10^{-10} M/ 6.7×10^{-12} M	PCR products from real samples	[143]
Hybridization at DNA probe immobilized on ECR ²⁹ monolayer film modified GCE	DPV (MB)	<i>PML::RARA</i> fusion gene (APL)	5.0×10^{-12} – 2.0×10^{-10} M/ 9.82×10^{-13} M	–	[141]
Sandwich hybridization with thiolated and biotinylated LNA capture and reporter probes at AuE	Chronoamperometry (HRP/TMB/H ₂ O ₂)	<i>PML::RARA</i> fusion gene (APL)	5.0×10^{-11} – 1.0×10^{-8} M (synthetic target)/ and 7.9×10^{-14} M/100- μ L hybridization system (PCR amplicons)	PCR products from NB4 cells	[170]
Hybridization at a dual-channel EC DNA sensor array based on the “Y” junction structure and restriction endonuclease assisted cyclic enzymatic amplification at AuEs	Chronoamperometry (HRP/TMB/H ₂ O ₂)	<i>PML::RARA</i> fusion gene (APL)	$-/4.7 \times 10^{-14}$ M	PCR products from NB4 cells, synthetic <i>PML::RARA</i> fusion gene	[142]
Dual probe sensing strategy involving two groups of 2-F RNA-modified probes and sandwich hybridization assays using thiolated capture probes and biotinylated reporter probes at AuEs	Chronoamperometry (HRP/TMB/H ₂ O ₂)	<i>PML::RARA</i> fusion gene (APL)	5.0×10^{-13} – 1.5×10^{-11} M/ 8.4×10^{-14} M	–	[171]
Hybridization at immobilized DNA probe on a CDs ³⁰ /GO ³¹ /GCE	DPV (MB)	<i>PML::RARA</i> fusion gene (APL)	2.50×10^{-10} – 2.25×10^{-9} M/ 8.30×10^{-11} M	–	[172]
Double-probe sandwich hybridization (thiolated and biotinylated capture and reported probes) and enzyme-mediated multiple signal electrocatalysis on d-AuE	Chronoamperometry (HRP/TMB/H ₂ O ₂)	<i>PML::RARA</i> fusion gene (APL)	5.0×10^{-13} – 5.0×10^{-11} M/ 7.1×10^{-14} M	PCR products and enzyme-digested PCR products from NB4 cells	[173]
Split-type EC sensor developed by integrating NASBA ³² , sandwich hybridization and enzyme-linked magnetic microbeads	Amperometry (HRP/TMB/H ₂ O ₂)	<i>PML::RARA</i> transcript (APL)	5.0×10^{-16} – 5.0×10^{-14} M and 5.0×10^{-14} – 1.0×10^{-11} M/ 1.0×10^{-16} M	Supplemented human serum samples and tRNA extracts from NB4 and K562 cells	[174]
Sandwich-mode EC DNA biosensor with LNA probes and biotinylated reporter probe	Amperometry (HRP/TMB/H ₂ O ₂)	<i>PML::RARA</i> fusion gene (Acute Promyelocytic Leukemia)	1.0×10^{-13} – 1.0×10^{-11} M/ 7.4×10^{-14} M	synthetic <i>PML::RARA</i> fusion gene	[140]
EC biosensor based on ECR film	DPV	<i>PML::RARA</i> fusion gene (APL)	5.0×10^{-12} – 2.0×10^{-10} M/ 9.82×10^{-13} M	synthetic <i>PML::RARA</i> fusion gene	[141]
DNA CP immobilized on GCE via CDs/PAMAM ³³ /rGO ³⁴ nanocomposites and an assistant probe labeled with Au@Ag ₂ S nanoparticles	ECL-RET	<i>PML::RARA</i> fusion gene (APL)	5×10^{-15} – 5×10^{-10} M/ 7.2×10^{-16} M	synthetic <i>PML::RARA</i> fusion gene	[175]
genosensor constructed from PPy ³⁵ and graphene QD on ITO substrates	CV, EIS	<i>PML::RARA</i> fusion gene (APL)	1.0×10^{-12} – 1.0×10^{-10} M/ 2.14×10^{-13} M (M7) and 6.77×10^{-13} M (APLB)	cDNA from APL patients, synthetic oligonucleotides for M7 and APLB (regions on chromosomes 15 and 17)	[176]
Hybridization at biotinylated DNA capture probe attached to streptavidin MBs and adsorption of target transcripts onto Au-SPEs	DPV ([Fe(CN) ₆] ^{3-/4-})	<i>TMPRSS2::ERG</i> fusion mRNA (PCa)	$-/10$ cells	Urinary samples from PCa patients	[146]
Integrated biochip comprised of on-chip electrical cell lysis, nanofluidic manipulation, isothermal solid-phase amplification of targets, and EC detection of immobilized amplicons via nanozyme-mediated redox reaction	Chronoamperometry (Nanozyme/TMB/H ₂ O ₂)	<i>TMPRSS2::ERG</i> gene fusion (PCa), PCA3, SchLAP1, and KLK2	$-/-$	Urinary samples from PCa patients	[149]

¹ LOD – limit of detection² GCE – glassy carbon electrode³ DPV – differential pulse voltammetry⁴ MB – methylene blue⁵ CP – capture probe⁶ SWV – square wave voltammetry⁷ LNA – locked nucleic acid⁸ STS – sodium tanshinone IIA sulfonate⁹ AuE – gold electrode¹⁰ HRP – horseradish peroxidase¹¹ TMB – tetramethylbenzidine

- ¹² Cu₂ – benzoate binuclear copper (II) complex
- ¹³ GNP – gold nanoparticles
- ¹⁴ MWCNT – multi-walled carbon nanotubes
- ¹⁵ PANI – polyaniline
- ¹⁶ EIS – electrochemical impedance spectroscopy
- ¹⁷ ITO – indium tin oxide
- ¹⁸ QcCdSe-SA-LB – Langmuir–Blodgett monolayers of tri-n-octylphosphine oxide-capped cadmium selenide quantum dots
- ¹⁹ CSRP – circular strand replacement polymerization
- ²⁰ QD – quantum dots
- ²¹ ASV – anodic stripping voltammetry
- ²² ERGNO – electrochemically reduced graphene oxide
- ²³ ISO – isorhamnetin
- ²⁴ Hb@AuNCs – Hb and gold nanoclusters composite
- ²⁵ LCR – ligation chain reaction
- ²⁶ PICA – poly(indole-5-carboxylic acid)
- ²⁷ CNT – carbon nanotubes
- ²⁸ polyCCA – poly-calcon carboxylic acid
- ²⁹ ECR – eriochrome cyanine R
- ³⁰ CD – carbon dots
- ³¹ GO – graphene oxide
- ³² NASBA – nucleic acid sequence-based amplification
- ³³ PAMAM – poly(amidoamine)
- ³⁴ rGO – reduced graphene oxide
- ³⁵ PPy – polypyrrole

minimizing the nonspecific interactions and enhancing the specificity. Lin’s use of a hairpin LNA probe provided a distinct structural feature that potentially enhances specificity and reduces background noise compared to the linear probe used by Chen et al. Again, the bioassay was tested on only one positive and one negative real PCR sample without specifying any details, limiting the evaluation of its clinical applicability and practical performance in biological settings.

Recently, a split-type EC biosensor coupled with an OR logic gate design was developed for the sensitive detection of ultra-low levels of the *BCR::ABL1* p210 transcript [133]. The biosensor utilizes enzyme-linked DNA magnetic beads based on a duplex ligation chain reaction (LCR), a PCR variant that detects specific mutations or genetic variations using two oligonucleotides that hybridize to adjacent regions

on a target single-stranded DNA (Fig. 2a). When these oligonucleotides perfectly match the target, a thermostable ligase enzyme joins them, and the resulting ligated products serve as templates for subsequent amplification cycles, enabling highly specific detection. LCR can be multiplexed to detect multiple mutations simultaneously. Biotin- and 6-FAM-labeled LCR products were captured on streptavidin-coated magnetic beads. Horseradish peroxidase (HRP)-conjugated anti-FAM antibodies subsequently bound to the DNA-magnetic bead complexes, which were magnetically assembled on a glassy carbon electrode. HRP then catalyzed the oxidation of tetramethylbenzidine (TMB) by H₂O₂, and the EC reduction of oxidized TMB at ~0.2 V was monitored by voltammetry and amperometry. This dual-amplification strategy enabled highly sensitive detection down to 1 aM with single-base

Fig. 2. A split-type EC biosensor coupled with a) LCR and b) OR logic gate design to detect *BCR::ABL1* p210 transcript. c) Amperometric responses obtained in the analysis of cDNA samples from newly diagnosed CML and ALL patients and from CML patients who had either received or were currently undergoing TKIs treatment. Reproduced with permission from Ref. [133].

specificity.

Additionally, poly(A) tails or fluorescent labels can be added to oligonucleotides for product differentiation based on size or for detection using sequencing-based systems, making LCR a robust tool for analysing mutations [134,135]. Their system could detect as few as 30 copies of the DNA target across a wide linear concentration range, offering high specificity at single-base resolution. Notably, the biosensor successfully detected K562 cells, which express the *BCR::ABL1* p210 isoform (b3a2), even when mixed with a 1,000-fold excess of NB4 cells, which are negative for *BCR::ABL1* p210 but positive for the *PML::RARA* fusion gene. This highlights the high specificity and practicality of the biosensor for use in complex sample mixtures. Moreover, the biosensor successfully detected the *BCR::ABL1* p210 transcript in both newly diagnosed CML patients (e14a2 and e13a2) and those who had completed TKI treatment, emphasizing its potential for the early diagnosis and monitoring of CML (Fig. 2b and c). This assay has several advantages, including low cost, ease of miniaturization, and broad applicability, making it a promising tool for clinical applications. Similar to the previously mentioned study, a significant drawback of this study is the lack of clinical samples from healthy donors. Additionally, although the authors claimed that their method could detect two different isoforms, they did not specify which clinical samples corresponded to the e14a2 and e13a2 isoforms. Moreover, important cell lines such as KCL-22, which is representative of the b2a2 isoform, are absent, limiting the scope of their findings. Nevertheless, this study represents an important step towards the clinical analysis of fusion genes using EC techniques.

To further improve sensitivity, various nanomaterials are often employed, such as two biosensors developed by Avelino et al. for *BCR::ABL1* detection. In the first study [136], the authors used an AuNP-polyaniline (PANI) hybrid composite in combination with thiol-modified probes on a gold electrode, with hybridization detected via DPV. The AuNPs provided a high surface area for DNA probe immobilization, while the conductive PANI matrix enhanced electron transfer at the electrode. Upon target hybridization, the negatively charged DNA backbone increased the interfacial resistance, leading to a measurable decrease in the peak current during DPV. This label-free transduction mechanism allows sensitive detection of DNA hybridization events without the need for additional enzymes or redox labels. The biosensor achieved an ultra-low limit of detection of 69.4 aM and demonstrated high specificity and sensitivity when tested with recombinant plasmid and 8 leukemia patient cDNA samples. The genosensor exhibited strong specificity, although highly concentrated negative samples produced slight non-specific responses. Patient samples validated the effectiveness of the biosensor, with clear differentiation between CML-positive and CML-negative cases. This biosensor demonstrated rapid label-free detection within 15 min, making it a promising alternative to PCR for leukemia diagnosis and minimal residual disease monitoring. Despite its strong performance, the limited real-sample testing suggests a need for broader clinical validation.

Later, the same group developed an EC DNA biosensor based on a hybrid nanostructure composed of chitosan and zinc oxide nanoparticles immobilized on a polypyrrole film, with oligonucleotide probes specific to the *BCR::ABL1* sequence. Using EIS and CV, Avelino's team achieved an impressive limit of detection (LOD) of 1.34 fM. In this design, the conductive polypyrrole film served as the backbone for efficient electron transport, while chitosan provided abundant functional groups for covalent immobilization of DNA probes. The incorporation of ZnO nanoparticles further enhanced the probe density and electrode surface area. Hybridization with the complementary target DNA introduced negatively charged phosphate groups, which hinder electron transfer between the electrode and redox probe. Validation was conducted using recombinant plasmid samples and clinical cDNA samples, which were analyzed within 15 min using only 2 μ L of the sample, which is a significant improvement over traditional methods. Although the biosensor demonstrated high sensitivity and specificity in detecting the *BCR::ABL1*

fusion gene in patients with CML, the limited inclusion of healthy control samples might have affected the comprehensive evaluation. A larger pool of healthy samples would provide more robust data on false-positive rates and further validate the biosensor performance in distinguishing between healthy individuals and CML patients [137]. Other nanomaterials that have been used for *BCR::ABL1* analysis include Fe₃O₄-functionalized carbon nanotubes [138] and poly(indole-5-carboxylic acid)-functionalized ZnO nanocomposites [139]; however, both were tested only on synthetic oligonucleotides, again questioning their potential for clinical application.

The *BCR::ABL1* fusion gene is the most common type of fusion gene targeted in EC studies; however, other fusion genes have also been reported. For example, Wang et al. published several studies on EC biosensors targeting the *PML::RARA* fusion gene. Each study explored different electrode modifications and amplification methods to enhance biosensor sensitivity and specificity for detecting target DNA sequences. In their 2011 study, they developed a sandwich-mode amperometric biosensor using LNAs on a gold electrode [140]. This sensor employs a pair of LNA probes, one immobilized on the electrode as a capture probe and the other as a biotinylated reporter probe. Streptavidin-HRP linked to the biotin tag on the reporter probe enabled signal amplification, resulting in an enzymatically amplified EC signal. HRP catalyzed the oxidation of TMB by H₂O₂, and the reduction of oxidized TMB was measured amperometrically using a gold electrode. This approach allowed the sensor to achieve a limit of detection of 74 fM with a linear range of 0.1–10 pM, showing high specificity by effectively discriminating against mismatch sequences. Subsequently, they reported an EC DNA biosensor for detecting *PML::RARA* based on a glassy carbon electrode modified with an eriochrome cyanine R (ECR) film [141]. The ECR film provides a stable platform for probe immobilization through covalent binding. DPV was used to measure the hybridization of the DNA probe with the target sequences using MB as an electroactive indicator. This biosensor exhibited a linear detection range of 5–200 pM, with a limit of detection of 0.982 pM. Compared to the LNA-based approach, the ECR film-modified sensor offers good selectivity, particularly for one-base mismatches, without requiring enzymatic signal amplification. In their next study, they introduced a dual-probe EC DNA biosensor for *PML::RARA* detection, leveraging a “Y” junction structure and restriction endonuclease-assisted cyclic enzymatic amplification (Fig. 3) [142]. In this setup, two groups of probes were designed to bind to each strand of the dsDNA target. This design provided a limit of detection of 47 fM and exhibited excellent specificity, even for distinguishing single-base mismatches in dsDNA sequences, and was applied to the detection of PCR products from NB4 cells (a positive control for APL). Each method demonstrated strong specificity, with the dual-probe system (2015) achieving the highest discrimination of single-base mismatches.

While previous studies on *PML::RARA* did not utilize any real samples, Zhong et al. developed an EC DNA biosensor based on a nanoporous gold (NPG) electrode for the detection of the *PML::RARA* fusion gene using PCR products from real samples [143]. The biosensor used MB as an electroactive indicator and DPV to monitor DNA hybridization. Upon hybridization of the probe DNA with the *PML::RARA* target sequence, the MB reduction signal decreased because of steric hindrance, enabling sensitive and selective detection. The biosensor demonstrated a linear detection range of 60–220 pM and an ultra-low limit of detection of 6.7 pM, highlighting its potential for detecting minimal residual disease in patients with APL.

Different biosensor for *PML::RARA* fusion gene analysis involves an enzyme-amplified EC biosensor using a hairpin LNA probe, which is dual-labeled with biotin and carboxyfluorescein (FAM) and immobilized on a streptavidin-coated electrode [144]. Upon hybridization with the target DNA, a conformational change exposes the FAM label, allowing the binding of antiFAM-HRP for enzyme-based signal amplification. The bound HRP catalyzed the oxidation of TMB by H₂O₂, and the EC reduction of oxidized TMB at the electrode surface was recorded. Both

Fig. 3. Dual-probe EC biosensor based on the “Y” junction structure and restriction endonuclease assisted cyclic enzymatic amplification for detection of *PML::RARA* fusion gene dsDNA. Reprinted with permission from Ref. [142].

CV and amperometric measurements were used, with the latter providing a more sensitive quantitative readout of the hybridization events. The biosensor demonstrated high specificity even when detecting single-base mismatches, achieving a LOD of 83 fM. To validate its practical application, the biosensor was tested using real blood samples. After PCR amplification, cDNA from NB4 cells (positive control) and blood samples were hybridized with the LNA probe and analyzed using amperometry. The biosensor successfully distinguished between positive and negative samples, showing clear differences in the current signals. The results correlated well with those obtained using traditional gel electrophoresis, confirming the accuracy and reliability of the sensor

[144]. These studies underscore the growing potential of EC platforms for leukemia diagnosis, offering promising tools for early detection, disease monitoring, and personalized therapy adjustments [143].

The detection of fusion genes in solid tumors poses unique challenges compared to hematological malignancies. Solid tumors exhibit higher heterogeneity, and tumor cells are often intermixed with normal tissue, making the extraction of high-quality nucleic acids more difficult [145]. Additionally, ctDNA and circulating tumor RNA (ctRNA) derived from solid tumors are often present in low concentrations in bodily fluids, which further complicates their detection. To overcome these limitations, emerging biosensing technologies, particularly EC biosensors,

Fig. 4. Amplification-free EC bioassay for detecting the *TMPRSS2::ERG* gene fusion comprising: a) extraction of tRNA from urine samples and isolation of the target mRNA using streptavidin-coated magnetic beads and b) adsorption of the isolated mRNA onto screen-printed gold electrodes and transduction by DPV in the presence of $[Fe(CN)_6]^{3-/4-}$. Reprinted with permission from Ref. [146].

have gained attention as promising alternatives for fusion gene detection in solid tumors owing to their high sensitivity.

In 2016, an interesting amplification-free study was reported for detecting *TMPRSS2::ERG* gene fusion directly from the urine samples of patients with prostate cancer [146]. The bioassay was based on the natural affinity between the polyA tail of the mRNA and the bare gold electrodes (Fig. 4). This method allowed for the direct adsorption of *TMPRSS2::ERG* mRNA onto a gold electrode surface, eliminating the need for surface modification or amplification. Biotinylated capture probes specific to the *TMPRSS2::ERG* gene fusion junction were used to isolate target mRNA from total RNA extracted from prostate cancer cells or urine samples. The captured mRNA was purified using streptavidin-coated magnetic beads (Fig. 4a). After isolating the target mRNA, it was adsorbed onto screen-printed gold electrode (Fig. 4b). EC detection was performed using the $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-/4-}$ redox pair, and DPV was used to quantify the amount of adsorbed mRNA. A decrease in the Faradaic current due to the negative charge of the adsorbed mRNA indicates the presence of target gene fusion. The assay could detect as few as 10 prostate cancer (PCa) cells, achieving LOD of 10 cells (~300 pg of RNA). It also showed excellent specificity, as no significant signal was observed when testing RNA from *TMPRSS2::ERG* cells (LnCap). The assay was tested on 17 urinary samples from patients with prostate cancer and demonstrated strong concordance with RT-qPCR, the current gold standard for gene fusion detection. The assay correctly identified 12 samples and provided reliable negative results for healthy controls and patients with *TMPRSS2::ERG*. The absence of enzymatic amplification simplifies the process, reduces costs, and minimizes the risk of amplification artefacts. The method provided rapid results using commercially available screen-printed gold electrodes and did not require expensive reagents or complex protocols. This amplification-free EC assay offers a promising platform for non-invasive detection of gene fusions in prostate cancer, with potential applications in point-of-care diagnostics. Its simplicity, sensitivity, and adaptability make it an attractive alternative to existing methods, such as RT-qPCR.

Fang et al. [147] developed a nanostructured microelectrode (NME) integrated circuit for EC detection of fusion gene transcripts directly from tumor tissues and cell extracts, without the need for PCR-based amplification [147]. This platform integrates microfabrication and bottom-up nanostructuring to enhance sensitivity and specificity, enabling rapid profiling of nucleic acid biomarkers associated with prostate cancer gene fusions, particularly *TMPRSS2::ERG* variants. This biosensor employs peptide nucleic acid (PNA) probes, which improve hybridization efficiency and reduce non-specific binding, thereby enhancing the overall performance of the detection system. Electro-catalytic redox cycling using ruthenium hexamine and ferricyanide further amplified the EC signal, and the process was monitored using CV and DPV. In this method, $\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_6^{3+}$ is bound electrostatically to the negatively charged nucleic acid backbone, and $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$ regenerates Ru (III). This led to multiple turnover cycles per molecule and the production of a strongly amplified current response. This strategy helped achieve a femtomolar limit of detection and increased discrimination between fully complementary and partially mismatched targets. Notably, the system was validated using mRNA extracted from prostate cancer cell lines (VCaP, DU145, and NCI-H660) and tumor tissues, demonstrating its potential as a clinically relevant diagnostic tool. This multiplexed EC biosensing approach allows for the direct detection of fusion genes within one hour using as little as 10 ng of RNA, significantly reducing the time and cost associated with conventional methods.

In the same year, Koo et al. developed the FusBLU assay for detecting *TMPRSS2::ERG* gene fusion utilizing a combination of an isothermal technique called reverse transcription recombinase polymerase amplification (RT-RPA) and HRP-catalyzed colorimetric and EC detection methods [148]. The FusBLU assay enabled colorimetric and EC detection of *TMPRSS2::ERG* gene fusion in clinical urine samples. RNA was extracted from whole urine, urinary sediments, and exosomes, and RT-RPA was used for amplification without thermal cycling.

Biotinylated dUTPs were incorporated into DNA, allowing magnetic isolation and HRP labeling. In the colorimetric mode, HRP reacts with $\text{TMB-H}_2\text{O}_2$ to produce a visible blue color that is detectable at 650 nm. For EC detection at screen-printed electrodes, HRP-catalyzed TMB oxidation generates a colored charge-transfer complex, which is protonated into a stable electroactive species upon addition of sulfuric acid. This allowed electron transfer at +0.15 V, producing a current that was proportional to the target DNA concentration.

The LOD for EC detection was 103 copies, which surpassed that of the colorimetric method. When tested on 12 prostate cancer patient samples, the assay correlated well with RT-qPCR. Urinary sediments exhibited the highest fusion mRNA levels. FusBLU is a rapid (75 min), cost-effective, and portable diagnostic tool that is adaptable for point-of-care and laboratory use, with potential applications beyond prostate cancer. Next work by Koo et al. introduced an EC biochip for sample-to-targeted genetic analysis of circulating tumor nucleic acids (ctNAs), incorporating nanofluidic-enhanced solid-phase amplification and chronoamperometric detection (Fig. 5) [149]. This biochip streamlines the entire diagnostic workflow, including on-chip electrical lysis of patient-derived samples, target capture, RT-RPA, and EC readout. The system utilizes superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles as nanozyme labels for peroxidase-mimicking signal amplification, enhancing detection sensitivity. During chronoamperometric detection, biotinylated amplicons generated using solid-phase RT-RPA were labeled with streptavidin-coated iron oxide nanozymes. Upon the addition of the $\text{TMB/H}_2\text{O}_2$ substrate, the nanozymes catalyzed TMB oxidation, producing electroactive species. A constant potential of +0.15 V was then applied for 30 s, and the resulting current provided a quantitative readout that was proportional to the target abundance. This method provided a low-background EC readout on-chip, which was capable of detecting as few as 50 copies per sample. Using prostate cancer as a model, the biochip successfully analyzed multiple clinically relevant genetic aberrations, including *TMPRSS2::ERG* gene fusion, *PCA3*, *SChLAP1*, and *KLK2* in serum and urine liquid biopsies. Furthermore, its multiplexing capability enables correlation studies between different biomarkers, thereby facilitating risk prediction, treatment monitoring, and cancer relapse detection. However, although the biochip demonstrated high sensitivity and specificity in prostate cancer samples, broader clinical validation across different cancer types and larger patient cohorts is necessary for clinical translation.

6. Conclusion

Bioelectroanalytical technologies continue to evolve, demonstrating extraordinary versatility in design and application to meet the demanding needs of precision diagnostics and therapeutics by discovering, identifying, and exploiting the potential of markers at different omics levels, including those that are particularly difficult to detect because of their nature and concentration. Among the latter are fusion genes, which are becoming increasingly important as markers for more accurate diagnostics and prognostics and for the application of the most effective therapies. This is why we have witnessed the development of numerous EC technologies for fusion gene detection. These advances are very significant, and most of the technologies are based on ingenious designs and offer very attractive performance and promising results for the detection of synthetic oligonucleotides and model systems. However, their limited application in the analysis of real-world samples raises questions regarding their use outside the research laboratory. The lack of validation in biological samples, such as patient-derived DNA or cell line experiments, means that the performance of these biosensors in complex biological matrices that may contain inhibitors or interfering substances remains uncertain. In addition, studies have predominantly focused on model targets and have not fully evaluated the ability of biosensors to detect fusion genes in various genomic contexts, which may present additional challenges, such as genetic variability or co-occurring mutations. Without testing in real-world scenarios, the

Fig. 5. Integrated EC biochip for sample-to-targeted genetic analysis of ctNAs. Reprinted with permission from Ref. [149].

sensitivity, specificity, and reliability of EC biosensors for fusion gene detection in clinical diagnostics and therapeutic monitoring remain inconclusive. Therefore, one of the major drawbacks of the current research is the poor translation of synthetic targets to biological or clinical samples, which is a critical step in the process.

Fortunately, several recent EC studies have addressed these challenges to demonstrate the potential usefulness of EC biosensors in clinical scenarios (as detailed in Section 5). The split-type EC biosensor coupled with LCR [133] not only successfully recognized BCR::ABL1 fusion in four CML patients (while confirming its absence in four ALL patients), but was also used to detect minimal residual disease (MRD) of CML, a critical marker used to assess the depth of molecular response to therapy, predict long-term remission, and guide decisions on treatment continuation or discontinuation. Although this is quite a challenging task due to the low expression levels of p210 after TKI treatment, biosensor showed good concordance with RT-qPCR for nine CML patients undergoing this treatment. Another highlight is a nanofluidic biochip utilizing RT-RPA to monitor cancer relapse in patients with prostate cancer [149]. Non-invasive relapse monitoring offers a valuable option for patients who can repeatedly provide urine or blood samples with minimal health risks and costs. This approach was demonstrated in five patients with prostate cancer: two who experienced relapse showed no significant decrease in *TMPRSS2::ERG* fusion levels (or other markers), whereas those who remained relapse-free exhibited lower expression levels.

However, translating bioelectroanalytical technologies for analysis of cancer biomarkers, including fusion gene detection, into clinical applications remains a complex endeavor, despite the rapid progress and considerable promise these systems offer in oncology diagnostics and therapy [177]. Most platforms are still in the early stages of technological readiness (TRLs 1–3), reflecting the wide range of regulatory, legal, ethical, and economic obstacles that must be addressed before clinical deployment becomes viable. One of the main challenges is the gap between academic development and commercialization. Transforming lab-scale prototypes into clinically approved tools requires close collaboration between disciplines such as research, engineering,

regulatory science, and industry. It is also a major challenge, and one that often comes with considerable financial and operational pressure, especially for newer and smaller companies, to meet the stringent validation and regulatory standards set by organizations such as the FDA and the EMA.

Ethical and social issues are also of concern, especially when these bioelectroanalytical technologies are intended to be integrated with mobile applications or cloud infrastructures, raising significant concerns regarding the need to obtain informed consent, maintain the confidentiality of patient information, and monitor individuals outside of clinical settings. In addition, current inequities in the healthcare system may be exacerbated by disparities in access to technological advances. From a technical perspective, the lack of consensus on the use of synthetic standards or standardized fabrication and characterization methods is a source of variability in sensor performance and reproducibility. In addition, although innovations in nanomaterials and interface design have been introduced to improve the sensitivity and specificity of these technologies, they also introduce greater complexity in manufacturing and increase production costs, which hinder their large scale adoption and use in low-resource environments. The need for exhaustive sample pretreatment when analyzing complex fluids, such as blood, also complicates the implementation of these devices in clinical settings.

However, while there seems little doubt that the ability of bioelectroanalytical devices to detect fusion genes can provide transformative potential for cancer diagnosis and personalized treatment, their premature clinical use without adequate validation could lead to misdiagnosis and inadequate care. Although significant challenges remain, we are confident that electroanalytical technologies will not give up and will continue to move towards real-world applications, playing a key role in unlocking the potential of these markers, supporting pharmaceutical development, and driving their integration into clinical practice to improve and democratize diagnosis and therapeutics.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Nasim Izadi: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Conceptualization. **Aneta Fried:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization. **Sarka Sevcikova:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. **Johana Strmiskova:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. **Ludmila Moranova:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. **Susana Campuzano:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Funding acquisition. **Martin Bartosik:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

The financial support of the Czech Science Foundation (No. 25-15990S), project SALVAGE (OP JAC; reg. no. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004644) – co-funded by the European Union and by the State Budget of the Czech Republic, MH CZ – DRO (MMCI, 00209805), the Grant PID2022-136351OB-I00 funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by “ERDF A way of making Europe” are gratefully acknowledged.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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